

**MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE AT A
NON-LINGUISTIC UNIVERSITY**

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Annotation: *The new requirements for student's education, which assume that they have relevant professional competencies, including foreign language communicative competence, actualize research attention to different approaches, technologies and conditions aimed at improving the quality of higher education. The article considers some innovative methods of teaching a foreign language at a non-linguistic university. On the basis of the conducted research, the author proves the need for innovative pedagogical technologies that would be effective and contribute to the progressive development of pedagogical science and prepare students for future professional activities.*

Key words: *modern methods, teaching methods for students of non-linguistic universities, teaching features, active methods.*

The transformation of society in the Republic of Uzbekistan according to an innovative scenario requires the training of highly qualified personnel capable of generating new knowledge and creating innovative world-class technologies [1–3]. The processes of implementation of the Bologna Declaration, the gradual entry of Uzbekistan into the world educational community led to the intensification of intercultural communication and significantly increased the importance of foreign languages for specialists in various fields. This immediately influenced the status of the “Foreign Language” discipline in non-linguistic educational organizations, since knowledge of a foreign language allows students to operate with information obtained from foreign-language sources, expands the professional range of a specialist of any profile. An understanding came that a modern student of a non-linguistic university (future engineer, economist, lawyer, and other specialists) needs to master a foreign language communicative competence that allows him to carry out professional activities in new conditions. Mastering a foreign language in a non-linguistic university is currently considered as an obligatory component of the professional training of a specialist of any profile, and possession of a foreign language communicative competence is one of the components of professional competence. The changing realities of the modern world require the same changes in educational systems [4–5]. In this regard, the topic of innovation is becoming important for the entire system of education and teaching a foreign language, in particular. As many years of practice show, modern methods of teaching foreign languages offer us a wide range of concepts

of the educational process, methods, and technologies — both traditional and innovative. Curriculum developers and teachers give preference to one method or another, depending on the learning objectives, the student population, the duration and intensity of the training course, and other conditions [6–7]. Moreover, each of the teaching methods has its own advantages and disadvantages, and the success of their application depends on the specific goals and conditions of training. In recent years, the role of a foreign language as a means of communication has significantly increased, which should be taken into account when teaching a language. The specificity of a foreign language is that we teach, not the basics of science, but skills and abilities, and this requires sufficient speech practice.

Material and research methods The studies of many authors have been devoted to the formation of students' linguistic competence in teaching a foreign language in non-linguistic universities, while such issues as the selection and content of educational material in teaching a foreign language were studied and highlighted (I. L. Bim [8], M. L. Vaysburd [9], N. D. Galskova [10], T. P. Ogluzdina [11], P. I. Obratsov [12]); psychological and pedagogical conditions for mastering a foreign language and the development of speech-thinking activity (A. L. Berdichevsky [13], Zh. M. Blieva [14], P. Ya. Galperin, G. N. Aleksandrov, V. P. Bepalko [15]); the formation of foreign language professional competence and the development of methodological approaches, technologies for teaching a foreign language (V. F. Aitov [16], T. N. Gorbunova, A. N. Leontiev [17], E. G. Trunova, A. A. Verbitsky [18] and etc.). However, despite a fairly large number of studies, it should be noted that modern teaching a foreign language at a university, and in particular in a technical one, needs a comprehensive improvement of the methods and means of professionally oriented teaching aimed at organizing practice-oriented educational activities, taking into account constantly updated requirements, achievements of pedagogical and psychological sciences. To solve the problems posed in accordance with the purpose of the study, and experimental verification of the hypothesis, a set of methods were used: theoretical methods — analysis of scientific and methodological, psychological and pedagogical literature, study of regulatory and program documentation on the research topic; empirical methods — questioning, testing, conversation, pedagogical experiment, self-assessment, expert assessment, observation.

Results and discussion The purpose of teaching a foreign language is not only to acquaint students with the system of a foreign language but, first of all, to teach how to use the language as a means of communication. Consequently, the entire structure of classes and the methods used, must correspond to the real situation of communication, and training must take place in the conditions of student interaction. The system of work of a teacher to ensure the results of teaching a foreign language must necessarily include the implementation of the following technologies: technology of communicative learning, technology of understanding the communicative meaning of a text, game technologies, learning technologies in cooperation, project technologies, etc. The concept of “technology” is borrowed from the sphere of production. According to the Philosophical Dictionary, edited by I. T. Frolov,

“technology is a complex developing system of artifacts, and processes, resource sources, subsystems of social consequences of information, management, financing and interaction with other technologies” [19]. In the UNESCO documents, “teaching technology” is considered already as a systematic method of creating, applying and defining the entire process of teaching and assimilating knowledge, taking into account technical and human resources and their interaction. In our opinion, pedagogical technologies of teaching a foreign language in a non-linguistic university should be understood as a set of forms, methods, teaching techniques and educational tools that are systematically used in the educational process. Innovations in the field of education are aimed at shaping the personality, its ability to scientific, technical and innovative activities, at updating the content of the educational process. With regard to the pedagogical process, innovation means the introduction of something new into the goals, content, methods and forms of teaching and upbringing, the organization of joint activities of the teacher and the student. Innovation in education means the possibility of including advanced scientific developments in the educational process, and in such a way that they allow training specialists who are able to independently carry out further innovations in the course of their scientific and practical career. The formation of innovative technologies for teaching foreign languages is caused by the need to overcome the crisis in education, which would contribute to the training of specialists of a new formation. The introduction of new technologies is also extremely important due to the fact that the new 21st century imposes different requirements on university graduates than the technocratic society of the 20th century. The teaching technology of the last century, based on the logic of science, on the principle "from knowledge to skills" should turn into a technology based on the laws of students' cognitive activity, that should be aimed at achieving the heights of professional, creative, spiritual and moral activity by graduates. In the new educational paradigm, the student is an active subject of cognitive activity, who, with the help of new forms of organizing the educational process, is involved in a dialogue with the teacher. A student today is an active, creative person who must not only possess a certain amount of knowledge, but also be able to learn, search and find the necessary information, use various sources for this, including media sources, and develop continuously [20]. The most important trends in the development of modern society associated with the processes of globalization and informatization are directly reflected in the educational process in general and in the field of foreign language education in particular. The conducted research and work experience shows that the current state of teaching foreign languages at a technical university can be characterized as a state of struggle between traditional teaching and innovation. Of course, the predominance of one type of learning leads to the extreme. If traditions prevail over the new, then stagnation, stagnation of science and practice will result, and if in the pursuit of innovations, we forget traditions, then science will have nothing to rely on. Therefore, an optimal balance of traditions and innovations is needed in order to move pedagogical science towards progress and development based on experience. We need technologies that

would be effective and contribute to the progressive development of pedagogical science and prepare students for future professional activities.

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